

METHODS OF RESEARCHING THE RESEARCH SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The methodological foundations of the development of student research skills in the higher education system are closely related, first of all, to psychological and pedagogical approaches that ensure the preparation of the individual for scientific activity. Based on these approaches, the student's abilities are formed, such as independent thinking, the ability to approach problem situations from a scientific perspective, mastering research technologies and analyzing scientific results.*

Keywords: *psychological and pedagogical approaches, independent thinking, knowledge acquisition, systematic and competency-based approaches, internal motivation, student individuality, motivational, intellectual, reflective, volitional, psychological mechanism.*

In the methodology for developing research skills, person-oriented, activity-based, systematic and competency-based approaches are of particular importance. The person-oriented approach allows the student to reveal his/her scientific potential, taking into account his/her individuality, internal motivation and interests. The activity-based approach, on the other hand, allows for the development of research skills to focus not on “acquiring knowledge”, but on the concept of “creating knowledge”. Within the framework of the systematic approach, research skills are seen as a complex mental structure consisting of interrelated components, and its development should be ensured in harmony at all levels (motivational, intellectual, reflective, volitional).

In determining the methodological foundations, the concepts of personality and activity of modern psychological schools, in particular, L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontiev, V.V. Davydov, B.G. Ananyev, D.A. Leontiev are of great theoretical importance, which substantiate the formation of research potential through the student's propensity for research, conscious reflection, metacognitive monitoring, and motivational needs. In particular, based on S.L. Rubinstein's principle of "personality is manifested in activity", the student's cognitive resources are maximally utilized by engaging in research activities. L.S. Vygotsky, through the concept of the "zone of proximal development", revealed the importance of scientific instructions and a supportive environment provided by mentors.

Diagnostic methods are also important in scientific and practical research aimed at methodologically assessing and developing research ability. To determine the level of scientific thinking of students, tests, questionnaires, observation, interview and assessment technologies are used. Based on the results obtained, students are divided into groups, and their level of ability, needs and development potential are determined. In empirical research, research ability is assessed mainly through the following psychological criteria: the level of independent thinking, the ability to understand and analyze a scientific problem, reasoning and proving, creative thinking, reflective approach, ability to evaluate results, the level of intellectual independence, the need to find new knowledge.

Another important area of methodological foundations is the development and implementation of educational technologies aimed at developing research skills. In this case, the educational process is organized on the basis of pedagogical technologies such as project-based learning, problem-based learning, inquiry-based learning (IBL), reflective learning, and experiential learning. Through such methods, the student realizes himself as a research subject, evaluates the results of his activities, and is directed to independent thinking. These approaches are methodological approaches that are widely used in international practice today. Thus, the methodology for developing students' research skills consists of a combination of a theoretical basis, psychological mechanisms, assessment criteria, and didactic technologies, and in this system there is an opportunity to reveal the scientific potential of the individual and turn him into an active researcher. Such methodological foundations embody the harmony of empiricism and theory, an individual approach aimed at development, and a professional-motivational system. The methodological foundations of the formation of research skills in students include four main components that are currently considered interrelated: epistemological foundations, psychological mechanisms, pedagogical conditions, and assessment criteria. Epistemologically, research is an independent form of cognitive activity in which the student conducts a directed search to achieve scientific truth. In this process, knowledge is not only received in a ready-made form, but is formed through the act of assimilation and re-creation. In such an approach, the creation of knowledge, rather than the consumption of knowledge, takes center stage, which involves the student in the learning process as an active participant. Among the psychological mechanisms, motivational preparation, reflective thinking, creative approach, metacognitive monitoring, and willpower stability are especially emphasized. The student is formed not only as a receiver of knowledge, but also as a person capable of creating new ideas through scientific research. In this process, his abilities to independently search for information, analyze problem situations, argue, put forward hypotheses, design experiments and evaluate them develop. It is these aspects that form the psychological foundations of research skills.

Pedagogical conditions represent a set of organizational and methodological opportunities necessary for the practical development of these abilities. These include elements such as scientific laboratories, project-based work opportunities, a mentoring system, participation in creative seminars, interactive lectures, independent research and preparation for scientific conferences. In order to awaken the need for scientific research in students and turn it into activity, the content and forms of education should be updated, as well as the teacher should take an active position as a scientific leader.

Assessment criteria represent tools that clearly indicate the level of research potential. These assessments are carried out qualitatively through the level of analytical thinking, the scope of use of scientific terminology, the ability to analyze the problem and propose a solution, the presence of an idea about methodological approaches, and the ability to conduct independent scientific reasoning. As diagnostic tools, specially designed tests, essays, scientific project defenses, interviews and observation protocols are used.

Also, for students to master research activities, the educational process must be methodologically sound, combining theoretical knowledge and practical activities, and systematically linking psychological preparation and methodological approaches. Only then can higher education institutions become centers for the formation of real researchers.

The research methods used were the “Test for assessing readiness for research activities” (O.I. Motkov), the “Methodology for assessing scientific research potential” developed by T.G. Stefanenko and V.V. Ovsyannikov, the questionnaire “Psychological readiness for innovative activities” by V.E. Klochko, O.M. Krasnoryadtseva and the questionnaire “Differential reflection type” (D.A. Leontyev, E.M. Lapteva, E.N. Osin, A.J. Salikhova), “Test for assessing readiness for research activity” (O.I.Motkov).

The “Diagnostics of aspiration for research activity” methodology developed by N.S.Pryaznikov is a psychodiagnostic tool that assesses the respondent’s internal need for research activity, motivational orientation, as well as self-awareness, dependence on the social environment and personal position in this area. The methodology serves to determine not the readiness of pupils or students for research, but their internal interest in this direction, aspiration, need for research, desire for independent thinking and openness to innovative activity. It is mainly intended for work with high school students, college and higher education students. This methodology is based on a multi-component system that determines the respondent’s ability to commit himself to scientific activity and intellectual and moral orientation.

Using the results of the methodology, a teacher or psychologist can determine what areas of reflective internal movements are active in a student, what aspects of him are more active in terms of motivation, as well as how ready and interested he is in scientific research. This methodology is used not only for diagnostic, but also for developmental purposes, for example, when guiding him in choosing a profession, selecting suitable candidates for scientific clubs or project work. Factor “Motivational-intellectual activity”: This factor measures the student’s internal desire for research activities, thirst for knowledge, need for independent thinking and need for intellectual satisfaction. A student with a high score on this factor usually strives for innovation, tries to find independent answers to his questions, and carries out scientific research with interest. Such a student seeks not only to complete tasks, but also to understand their reasons, which indicates his ability to think deeply. He enjoys the process of acquiring knowledge, which serves him as a strong psychological foundation for solving any complex scientific problems. A motivationally active person does not passively approach the study of information, but processes it, analyzes it and gives it new meaning. He is constantly looking for novelty, seeks to expand his knowledge, and enjoys intellectual debate. Such a student, relying on his mental capabilities, acts in an independent direction, not within the framework of the direction given by the teacher. At the same time, his thinking is flexible, he quickly adapts to understanding various scientific situations, and finds creative solutions to the problem. The development of this factor gives him the potential to conduct deep and meaningful research in scientific activity in the future.

“Awareness of the social significance of research” factor: This factor reflects the student’s understanding of how the results of scientific activity can benefit society, as well as the desire to find solutions to social problems through their research. Such a student realizes that their scientific project should serve society, not only for personal development. He sees scientific activity not only as a skill in an academic context, but also as a tool for responding to global social needs. Students with a strong sense of social responsibility have a sense of social responsibility and consider the collective good to be a priority in their research. They prefer scientific activity that serves to solve urgent problems in the fields of human health, ecology, education, or technology. These students strive to connect their knowledge with the needs of society and turn their personal research into social benefit. Therefore, they act with the motivation to serve a social goal, not only

for individual success, but also for the implementation of their projects. The student deeply understands how the results of his activities are reflected in society, which encourages him to take a responsible approach to his knowledge. This factor, in particular, serves to form competencies based on the understanding of the integral connection "science - practice - society". As a result, the student begins to evaluate his scientific potential in a global context, which raises his intellectual status to a higher level.

Factor "Confidence in one's own scientific potential": This factor expresses the student's confidence in his/her own ability to conduct scientific research, express independent opinions, analyze scientific problems and solve them. Students with high scores on this factor freely express their ideas, do not hesitate to participate in debates and logically substantiate their opinions. They are active in scientific assignments, are ready to rely on their own opinion and substantiate it with evidence. This confidence strengthens their confidence in taking personal initiative, participating in scientific seminars and conferences, and presenting results. The student realizes the importance of his/her opinion, which leads him/her to have a free and strong position in interpersonal communication. Confidence in scientific potential, in turn, causes the student to feel like an important participant in the research process. From a psychological point of view, this situation forms a whole system of self-awareness, social comparison, positive expectations of success and self-support. Such students do not look at scientific activity with fear or doubt, but as an opportunity. A student who believes in his scientific potential is not afraid of even complex problems and begins to solve them step by step. They feel like an equal member of the scientific community, which leads them to a higher level of motivation.

Factor "Connecting research activities with one's own life": This factor expresses the extent to which a student can combine scientific activity with his personal life, professional development and future work. Such students have the belief that science, research and analysis should be an integral part of their lifestyle. They believe that scientific research is necessary not only for professional growth, but also for self-realization, personal satisfaction, inner aspirations and spiritual growth. For them, science is not just a task to be performed in the classroom, but a type of activity that has become a vital necessity and an internal need. During the training process, such students have enriched their scientific views with personal experience, which has led to the formation of a deep and consistent approach to their activities. They openly declare their readiness to connect their future precisely with research and indicate scientific research as a central place in their personal life plans. For these students, scientific activity is not a social status, but an expression of personal identity. Psychologically, this factor indicates the strength of internal motivation in the student, the stability of life goals and the ability to consciously plan their capabilities. They try to understand any values in life on a scientific basis, which deepens their worldview. Thus, a student who is able to connect research activities with his life develops into a psychologically strong individual who maintains internal harmony between his actions, goals and values.

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